

Data Curation Policy

COPLI: Creating a FAIR open Science Pipeline for high-resolution
LOFAR imaging

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1 Purpose

This policy defines how data generated and used in this and related projects are stored, preserved, and shared. Its aim is to ensure data quality, reproducibility, and long-term usability in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

2 Scope

This policy applies to all data produced within and related to COPLI, including:

- Processed and derived data products
- Data required for validation or reproducibility
- Associated metadata

3 Data Formats

Data should be stored using widely accepted, non-proprietary formats where possible. Including:

- **FITS**: Images, source catalogues
- **HDF5**: Calibration solutions
- **MeasurementSets (MS)**: Visibility data
- **PNG**: Diagnostic plots and thumbnails

4 Data to be retained

The following data *must* be preserved:

- Final science-ready FITS images used for analysis or publications
- Associated PyBDSF or equivalent source catalogues
- Calibration solutions for inspection and reproducibility (e.g. HDF5 products)
- Scripts, configuration, and parset files required to reproduce manual processing steps that modified the output data outside the automated pipeline

The following data *may* also be preserved:

- Calibrated Measurement Sets
- Diagnostic and inspection plots
- Log files

5 Software Curation and Preservation

- All software used for data processing and analysis must be version-controlled in a persistent repository (e.g. Git)
- Published results must reference specific software versions using commit hashes or tagged releases, or provide a link to an online repository containing the scripts for reproducibility
- Where possible, software used in publications should be publicly accessible
- Computational environments (e.g. singularity/apptainer containers) should be preserved to ensure reproducibility

6 Metadata and Provenance

6.1 Metadata requirements

All datasets must be accompanied by sufficient metadata to enable interpretation and reuse. This includes:

- Instrument name
- Observation IDs
- Frequency range
- Resolution
- Image sizes
- Central coordinates of observation
- Coordinate system information
- Date of observation

6.2 Provenance

The history of each published dataset must be recorded, including:

- Processing steps
- Input and output datasets for each step
- Timestamps of processing events
- Software, scripts, and pipeline versions used

7 Data release

7.1 Storage

- Data must be stored on secure, collaboration-approved or institutional systems
- Published data should be available for a minimum of 5 years

7.2 Access

- Access to pre-publication data is restricted to authorised project members
- Following publication, data should be made publicly accessible where possible
- Sensitive or restricted data must be appropriately protected

7.3 Retention period

- Minimum retention requirements: Raw and final datasets: ≥ 5 years
- Metadata and provenance records: Indefinite retention recommended
- Published data products: Must remain accessible via persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI)
- If data are withdrawn or no longer available, the associated persistent identifier must resolve to a tombstone landing page describing the dataset and the reason for removal

7.4 Repositories

Data should be deposited with DOIs in trusted repositories (e.g. LOFAR Long-Term Archive, SURF Data Repository, Zenodo) for long-term access and citation.

8 Quality Assurance

- Data must be checked for completeness and consistency during ingestion
- Validation should be performed after major processing steps
- Errors and anomalies must be recorded and, where possible, corrected

9 Data Ownership

Data generated within the project are collectively owned by the collaboration, unless otherwise specified by external data providers.